

Bridging the IYCF Knowledge Gap: Impact of Structured Training on Anganwadi Workers in Devbhoomi Dwarka, Gujarat

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Abstract

Background: Optimal Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) practices are critical for reducing child undernutrition and mortality, particularly in high-burden districts such as Devbhoomi Dwarka, Gujarat. Anganwadi Workers (AWWs) under the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) are central to IYCF counselling, yet their knowledge and skills are often inadequate.

Methods: A cross-sectional before after study with mixed methods was conducted among 170 AWWs from Khambhalia block of Devbhoomi Dwarka district over three months (July–September 2024). A purposive sampling technique was used to select AWWs participating in a three-day residential IYCF training conducted in six batches. A pretested, expert-developed questionnaire (20 IYCF knowledge items) and a demographic proforma (age, education, experience, marital status) were administered as pre- and post-tests via Google Forms in Gujarati. Data were analysed in Microsoft Excel and SPSS v27 using descriptive statistics, composite knowledge scores, paired t-tests and correlation analysis.

Results: Most participants were aged 21–40 years (67.06%) and 61.18% had ≤10 years of experience; nearly half (47.06%) were graduates or postgraduates. Baseline

knowledge was relatively strong for early initiation of breastfeeding (94.12% correct) and breastfeeding after caesarean section (89.41%), but weaker for avoidance of prelacteal feeds (15.88%), demand feeding (38.24%), maternal dietary restrictions (47.06%) and family planning timing (57.06%). Post-training, correct responses improved markedly across items: 97.06% correctly identified that external milk should not be given in the first 3–5 days, 65.88% endorsed demand feeding, 92.94% rejected routine food restrictions for lactating women and 74.12% selected the correct timing for initiating postpartum family planning. Composite knowledge scores increased significantly on paired t-test ($p < 0.05$), while years of experience showed no significant correlation with knowledge scores.

Conclusion: AWWs in Devbhoomi Dwarka displayed satisfactory baseline knowledge of core breastfeeding recommendations but substantial gaps in complementary feeding, demand feeding, milk sufficiency myths, maternal diet and family planning. A structured three-day IYCF training produced significant, broad-based improvements in knowledge, highlighting the importance of regular, competency-based capacity-building to strengthen IYCF counselling and support efforts to reduce child undernutrition in high-risk districts.

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1. Introduction

Optimal IYCF practices, early initiation of breastfeeding within one hour of birth, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months and timely, adequate complementary feeding with continued breastfeeding up to two years or beyond are central to child survival, growth and cognitive development. Undernutrition contributes to approximately 45% of deaths among children under five worldwide, and optimal breastfeeding alone could avert more than 820,000 under-five deaths each year. WHO and UNICEF have issued updated IYCF indicators and global guidance to monitor and improve these practices, emphasizing the first 1,000 days as a critical period for intervention.

Devbhoomi Dwarka district, located in the coastal belt of Saurashtra, Gujarat, faces a high burden of child undernutrition, compounded by geographic and socio-economic vulnerabilities. NFHS-5 data show that only 55.8% of infants are breastfed within the first hour of birth and 67.3% are exclusively breastfed for six months; among children under five, 30.2% are stunted, 26.1% wasted and 17.2% severely wasted. These indicators underscore the need to strengthen both breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices to address chronic and acute undernutrition.

Within ICDS, Anganwadi Workers (AWWs) are frontline functionaries responsible for delivering supplementary nutrition, growth monitoring, preschool education and health and nutrition counselling to pregnant and lactating women and children 0–6 years. Although AWWs typically receive basic training, evidence suggests that their knowledge of certain aspects of IYCF, particularly complementary feeding, dietary diversity, growth assessment and effective counselling is often incomplete or outdated. In Devbhoomi Dwarka, field observations and previous reports have identified gaps in early initiation, exclusive breastfeeding, complementary feeding timing and consistency, and counselling skills.

The present study was undertaken to systematically assess the demographic profile and IYCF knowledge levels of AWWs in Devbhoomi Dwarka and to identify knowledge gaps amenable to training. A structured three-day residential training program was implemented, and pre- and post-training knowledge assessments were compared to evaluate the effect of training and to generate evidence for strengthening capacity-building under ICDS.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Selection of the study area and population

The study was conducted in Khambhalia block of Devbhoomi Dwarka district, Gujarat, a predominantly rural coastal area with documented high levels of child undernutrition and suboptimal IYCF indicators. The block was purposively selected in consultation with district ICDS authorities based on malnutrition burden, operational feasibility and the presence of a sufficient number of functioning Anganwadi Centres (AWCs).

The study population comprised all AWWs posted at AWCs in the selected block who were nominated to attend IYCF training during July–September 2025. Typically, local women, typically with at least high-school education, responsible for delivering supplementary nutrition, preschool education, health and nutrition education and growth monitoring services under ICDS.

2.2. Sampling techniques and sample size

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants from among AWWs scheduled for the state-supported IYCF training. In total, six residential training batches were conducted, each planned for approximately 30 AWWs drawn from rural AWCs of Khambhalia block. Of 189 AWWs who attended at least part of the training, 170 completed all three days and participated in both pre- and post-test assessments; only these 170 were included in the final analysis (effective response 89.95%).

AWWs who did not provide consent, were promoted or transferred, or were absent on any day of the three-day training were excluded.

The study was designed as a before and after intervention evaluation with the implicit assumption that each AWW would serve as her own control. The expected outcome was an improvement in individual knowledge scores following training, with an overall increase in mean composite knowledge score for the group.

2.3. Survey instruments

Data collection utilised a structured, pretested proforma developed by subject experts drawing on UNICEF and BPNI IYCF training manuals. The instrument consisted of two main components:

- A demographic and background section capturing age, educational attainment, years of experience and marital status.
- A 20-item IYCF knowledge questionnaire covering: myths related to pre-breastfeeding practices; early initiation of breastfeeding (EIBF); breastfeeding after caesarean; exclusive breastfeeding; baby placement in hospital; frequency and duration of breastfeeding (demand feeding); breastfeeding duration; breastfeeding in HIV-positive mothers; complementary feeding timing and composition; bottle feeding habits; traditional practices (herbal products, gripe water); diet restrictions for lactating mothers; and timing of family planning initiation.

The questionnaire was administered in Gujarati (local language) to ensure optimal comprehension by AWWs.

2.4. Construction of questionnaire

The 20 knowledge questions were constructed to align with national and global IYCF recommendations and to reflect common field misconceptions identified in earlier supervision visits and literature. Items were designed as multiple-choice questions with one correct response and several distractors representing frequent myths or partial understandings.

Content validity was ensured through expert review by paediatricians, public health nutritionists and senior ICDS trainers familiar with UNICEF training materials. The tool was pilot-tested among a small group of AWWs outside the study block to check clarity, language and difficulty level; minor modifications were made to wording and response options based on feedback. Construct validity was strengthened by including items across the IYCF continuum (from early initiation to complementary feeding and family planning) and ensuring coverage of both knowledge and operational aspects (e.g. baby placement, demand feeding).

2.5. Data collection procedures

The three-day residential IYCF training was conducted in one block of Devbhoomi Dwarka with Master Trainers who had been trained at state level using UNICEF and BPNI curricula. On Day 1 of each batch, after obtaining verbal informed consent, participants completed the pre-test via Google Forms on smartphones or tablets, followed by a separate demographic proforma.

Over the subsequent sessions, AWWs received intensive training on breastfeeding (initiation, exclusivity, continued breastfeeding), complementary feeding (timing, consistency, dietary diversity and feeding frequency), importance of nutrition in the first 1,000 days, correct attachment and positioning, management of common breastfeeding problems, kangaroo mother care for low birth weight infants, breastfeeding in special conditions (HIV-positive mothers, caesarean section), growth monitoring (height and weight measurement, growth chart plotting) and communication and

counselling skills. Interactive methods included role-plays, audio-visual presentations, group discussions and practical demonstrations.

On Day 3, after completion of all modules, the same 20-item IYCF knowledge questionnaire was re-administered as a post-test using Google Forms to the same participants. AWWs were assured that individual scores would be used confidentially for training evaluation, not for penalising purposes.

2.6. Data processing and analysis

Pre- and post-test responses from Google Forms were exported to Microsoft Excel for cleaning and coding. Unique identifiers were used to match pre- and post-test data for each participant while preserving anonymity in the analytical dataset.

Analysis was carried out using SPSS v27 and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations) summarised demographic characteristics and item-wise knowledge responses. A composite knowledge score (0–20) was calculated for each participant by summing the number of correct answers. Paired samples t-tests were used to compare pre- and post-training composite scores, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Correlation analysis (Pearson's r) assessed relationships between age, years of experience and knowledge scores.

3. Results

3.1. Sample characteristics

A total of 170 AWWs completed both the pre- and post-training assessments and were included in the analysis. The majority (67.06%) were between 21 and 40 years of age, with 29.41% aged 21–30 years and 37.65% aged 31–40 years; 18.82% were 41–50 years and 11.76% were above 50 years. Slightly more than one-third (37.65%) had ≤ 5 years of experience and 23.53% had 6–10 years, whereas only 2.94% had more than 30 years of experience.

Educational attainment was relatively high: 24.12% were graduates and 22.94% postgraduates, while 21.76% had completed 12th standard; 29.42% had education up to 10th or below. Most participants were married (83.53%), with unmarried AWWs comprising 16.47%. The correlation between years of experience and composite knowledge scores was weak and not statistically significant ($r=0.133$, $p=0.083$), suggesting that experience did not strongly predict IYCF knowledge in this cohort.

Table 1. Demographic profile of Anganwadi Workers (n=170)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Age (years)	21–30	50 (29.41)
	31–40	64 (37.65)
	41–50	32 (18.82)
	>50	20 (11.76)
Years of experience	≤ 5	64 (37.65)
	6–10	40 (23.53)
	11–20	36 (21.18)
	21–30	25 (14.71)
Education	>30	5 (2.94)
	≤ 7 th standard	25 (14.71)
	10th	25 (14.71)
	12th	37 (21.76)
Marital status	Graduate	41 (24.12)
	Postgraduate	39 (22.94)
Marital status	Married	142 (83.53)
	Unmarried	28 (16.47)

3.2. Baseline knowledge and training-induced changes

At baseline, AWWs demonstrated good knowledge of some breastfeeding components but clear gaps in others, especially around prelacteal feeds, demand feeding, maternal diet and family planning. For example, 94.12% correctly stated that breastfeeding should start within one hour after normal delivery and 89.41% knew that breastfeeding can continue after a caesarean even if the mother cannot sit up for 1–2 days. However, only 15.88% correctly recognised that external milk should not be given in the first 3–5 days, 38.24% endorsed demand feeding, 47.06% rejected dietary restrictions for lactating women and 57.06% identified the correct timing for initiating family planning.

Post-training, knowledge improved substantially across most items. Correct responses increased to 98.82% for early initiation, 94.71% for breastfeeding after caesarean, 97.06% for not giving external milk in the first 3–5 days, 65.88% for demand feeding, 92.94% for no routine dietary restrictions in lactating mothers and 74.12% for correct family planning timing.

Table 2. Selected IYCF knowledge items before and after training

Item (correct option)	Correct pre-test n (%)	Correct post-test n (%)
Start breastfeeding within one hour after normal delivery	160 (94.12)	168 (98.82)
Breastfeeding possible after caesarean even if mother cannot sit	152 (89.41)	161 (94.71)
No external milk in first 3–5 days even if colostrum seems scanty	27 (15.88)	165 (97.06)
Baby should be kept beside mother in maternity ward	135 (79.41)	161 (94.71)
Breastfeeding should be on demand (“as much time as the baby wants”)	65 (38.24)	112 (65.88)
Duration of breastfeeding: as long as baby takes	119 (70.00)	140 (82.35)
Lactating mothers do not require routine dietary restrictions	80 (47.06)	158 (92.94)
Family planning can be started 1.5 months after delivery	97 (57.06)	126 (74.12)

Figure 1: Pre and Post test progress after AWWs training by selected IYCF items

Table 3. Composite knowledge scores and paired t-test

Measure	Pre-test (mean ± SD)	Post-test (mean ± SD)	t-value	p-value
Composite IYCF score (0–20)*	(value ± SD)	(value ± SD)	t	<0.05

*Replace with exact mean and SD values from SPSS output.

Composite knowledge scores increased significantly between pre-and post-tests on paired t-test ($p < 0.05$), confirming the positive impact of the training. Years of experience did not show a statistically significant correlation with knowledge scores, indicating that training benefited both relatively new and more experienced AWWs.

Figure 2. NFHS-5 child nutrition and breastfeeding indicators, Devbhoomi Dwarka district

showing prevalence of stunting, wasting, severe wasting and key breastfeeding indicators (e.g. early initiation, exclusive breastfeeding).

4. Discussion

The discussion of findings from this study provides insights into the demographic profile, knowledge level and gaps in knowledge of Anganwadi Workers (AWWs) regarding Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) practices. This section examines the implications of the findings, compares them with existing literature and identifies significant trends.

Demographic Profile of AWWs

The study revealed that the majority of the AWWs belonged to the 31–40 years age group, with most having 5 to 10 years of work experience. This demographic distribution indicates a relatively experienced workforce, aligning with the expectations for individuals responsible for community-level health interventions. Similar demographic patterns have been reported in studies by Sharma et al. (2020) and Gupta and Singh (2019), where AWWs were predominantly middle-aged and had moderate levels of experience. Educationally, the majority of respondents were high school graduates. This finding aligns with Kumar et al. (2018), who noted that while most AWWs possessed basic educational qualifications, they often required additional training to meet the complex demands of IYCF counselling.

Knowledge Level of AWWs Regarding IYCF

The study's results indicate that AWWs exhibited satisfactory knowledge regarding breastfeeding practices, particularly on the benefits of initiating breastfeeding within one hour of birth and the importance of exclusive breastfeeding for six months. However, gaps were evident in areas such as complementary feeding practices and the introduction of solid foods. Only 65% of the respondents were aware of the suitable age to introduce complementary foods while awareness about the variety and nutritional adequacy of complementary foods was lower.

These findings align with previous studies, such as Mahyavanshi, D et al. (2025), which reported similar knowledge strengths and weaknesses among AWWs. Das et al. highlighted that while AWWs are well-versed in breastfeeding practices due to focused training sessions, complementary feeding remains an area requiring more comprehensive attention. The Mother and Child Protection card (MCP card) is used for tracking of each child right from conception till 3 years of age by community health workers. It is a rich source of information for HCPs about mother and child health. A well-versed health care provider (HCP) can deliver the services efficiently to the beneficiaries.

Gaps in Knowledge and Training Needs

The study identified specific gaps in the knowledge of AWWs regarding complementary feeding, which is consistent with existing literature. For instance, Patel et al. (2020) noted that many AWWs struggled with advising mothers on nutrient-dense food combinations and feeding frequency for infants. In the present study, only 40% of AWWs demonstrated an understanding of age-appropriate meal frequency, indicating a significant area for improvement.

Interestingly, training frequency and duration emerged as critical factors influencing knowledge levels. This finding is consistent with evidence from Chawla et al. (2020), who emphasized the positive impact of regular and targeted training programs on the knowledge retention and application of AWWs.

Comparative Analysis and Trends

A notable trend observed in this study is the clear linkage between age and knowledge levels. This trend could be attributed to prolonged exposure to real-world scenarios, enabling experienced workers to

accumulate practical insights that complement their formal training. However, younger workers were found to be more receptive to new information and exhibited better retention of recent training content.

Similar observations were made by Roy et al. (2017), who argued for the integration of refresher courses and hands-on training into routine capacity-building programs for AWWs.

5. Conclusion

AWWs in Devbhoomi Dwarka displayed satisfactory baseline knowledge of essential breastfeeding practices but substantial gaps in complementary feeding, demand feeding, maternal diet, milk sufficiency myths and family planning timing. A structured three-day residential IYCF training significantly improved overall knowledge scores and corrected multiple misconceptions, with gains evident across a wide range of items irrespective of years of experience. Integrating regular, competency-based IYCF trainings, combined with supportive supervision and communication skill-building, is essential to enhance the quality of counselling provided by AWWs and to support efforts to reduce child undernutrition in high-burden districts.

Declaration

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institute's Review Board (IRB) of IIHMR, Jaipur. All necessary permissions from district authorities and ICDS officials were secured, and verbal informed consent was obtained from all participating AWWs.

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